

Potential anthelmintic properties of selected medicinal plants in Brunei Darussalam: a phytochemical review

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Abstract

Parasitic infections caused by nematode parasites are a challenge which causes significant threats to animal health, which results in economic losses. Medicinal plants have been utilised for generations as traditional remedies against various diseases due to the presence of bioactive compounds in the plants. This article reviews four selected plant species in Brunei: *Azadirachta indica*, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Clitoria ternatea*, and *Litsea elliptica* to unravel their potential in combating helminthic infections, considering both their historical significance and known therapeutic values. The phytochemical compounds present in each species that exhibit potential anthelmintic properties are discussed and evaluated. The selected medicinal plants from Brunei have shown their potential as an alternative anthelmintic source, particularly noting their effectiveness against nematode parasites due to the presence of phytochemicals in the plants. *Caenorhabditis elegans* can be used as a model organism to explore the exact active compounds having anthelmintic ability and elucidate its mechanism of action to enhance a better understanding of plant-based anthelmintics and their potential in combating nematode parasitic infections. Hence, the identification and understanding of the phytochemical constituents of these plants can offer promising avenues for the development of novel interventions to combat parasitic infections in livestock, promoting sustainable agricultural practices and securing food production.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, helminth infection, nematode, *Caenorhabditis elegans*

Introduction

Brunei Darussalam, a small equatorial country located in Borneo Island, is widely known for its abundance of natural resources. The economy of Brunei is heavily relied on the income generated from crude oil and natural gas exports, contributing around 50 percent to the country's Gross Domestic Product (Department of Economic Planning and Statistics, 2022). Recognising the importance of sustainable development, the Brunei government has attempted to diversify the economy and reduce the dependence on non-renewable resources since the late 20th century (Hoon *et al.*, 2023). As part of this shift, agriculture and food security have been one of the identified key sectors for investment and innovation (Radzuan *et al.*, 2022).

The progress in agricultural technology has played a pivotal role in enhancing yield and productivity in various agricultural sectors, including the livestock industry. Despite these advancements, challenges persist, especially in the mass production of the livestock. A noteworthy obstacle is the widespread occurrence of parasitic infections in agricultural settings, particularly those caused by nematode parasites. These parasites cause a significant threat to animal health, which result in economic losses (Charlier *et al.*, 2014). Synthetic anthelmintic drugs are usually required to control the parasitic worm infections. However, the usage of these modern drugs is recently restricted due to the high cost and increasing development of helminth resistance (Kaplan, 2004).

An efficient alternative source for anthelmintic drugs is derived botanical, which can provide a simple and sustainable method of controlling the parasitic worms. Therefore, there is an urgent need for novel anthelmintic drugs against intestinal parasitic nematodes derived from herbal sources. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the bioprospecting of plant species to discover natural compounds with anthelmintic properties (Veerakumari, 2015). The medicinal plants that are often used in the traditional medicine can offer a wide repository of knowledge, which can be leveraged to identify active compounds against parasitic infections. Brunei Darussalam, renowned for its rich biodiversity and distinctive flora due to the diverse ecosystems, hence, is providing an ideal habitat for the diverse range of plant species with multitude medicinal value. The medicinal plants have been utilised for generations as traditional remedies against various diseases due to the presence of bioactive compounds in the plants. This article reviews four selected plant species with renowned medicinal properties in Brunei: *Azadirachta indica*, *Andrographis paniculata*, *Clitoria ternatea*, and *Litsea elliptica* to unravel their potential in combating helminthic infections, considering both their historical significance, and known therapeutic values.

This review explores the phytochemical profiles of the selected plants to identify active compounds with potential anthelmintic properties. This will in turn, help to uncover novel therapeutic interventions of Brunei Medicinal plants against parasitic nematodes.

***Azadirachta indica* (Sugi India)**

Azadirachta indica is a medium sized tree belonging to Meliaceae family (Table 1). It is commonly known as neem or “Sugi India” in Malay (Table 2), Neem has an average height of 30 meters with exterior bark of dark grey and reddish interior. The leaves are green in colour, alternate, and clustered at the tips of the branches. The fruit of the neem tree is a drupe that undergoes a colour transformation from green to yellow as it ripens (Nicoletti, 2020).

A. indica is originated from India and has been widely distributed and cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions. For thousands of years, neem has been recognized for its multitude beneficial properties, including those in agriculture for pest control and in traditional medicine for various common human ailments. The herb has been used for the treatment of diseases including skin disorders, digestive problems, respiratory issues, infections, wound healing, dental, and other healing and protective properties (Puri, 1999; Subapriya & Nagini, 2005; Kumar & Navaratnam, 2013; Wylie and Merrell, 2022; Haji *et al.*, 2023)

Table 1

Taxonomic classification of A. indica, A. paniculata, L. elliptica and C. ternatea. Data derived from Ngearnsaengsaruy *et al.* 2011; Hossain *et al.* 2014; Sarkar *et al.* 2021 and Suarna and Wijaya, 2021.

	<i>A. indica.</i>	<i>A. paniculata</i>	<i>L. elliptica</i>	<i>C. ternatea</i>
Kingdom	Plantae			
Division	Magnoliophyta	Angiosperma	Magnoliophyta	Magnoliophyta
Order	Rutales	Personales	Magnoliopsida	Fabales
Suborder	Rutinae			
Family	Meliaceae	Acanthaceae	Lauraceae	Fabaceae
Subfamily	Melioideae	Acanthoideae		Faboideae
Tribe	Melieae	Justiciae		Phaseoleae
Genus	Azadirachta	Andrographis	Litsea	Clitoria
Species	Indica	Paniculata	Elliptica	Ternatea

Table 2

Vernacular names for respective species of plants: A. indica, L. elliptica, A. paniculata and C. ternatea.

Country	<i>A. indica</i>	<i>L. elliptica</i>	<i>A. paniculata</i>	<i>C. ternatea</i>
Brunei/Malaysia	Sugi India	Pawas	Hempedu Bumi	Telang
Indonesia	Intaran, Mimba	Medang Perawas	Sambiloto	Kembang Telang
Thailand	Saliang, Sadao	Tham-mung	FaThalai Chon	Anchan
Phillipines	Nim, Balunga	Batikuling- surutan	Sinta, Aluy	Pokindong, Kolokanting
India	Neem		Kalmegh	Aparajitha

Phytochemistry of *Azadirachta indica*

Numerous studies have investigated the phytochemical composition of different parts of neem using various extraction methods and solvents (Puri, 1999; Yakubu *et al.*, 2006; Seriana *et al.*, 2021). Phytochemical substances that are present in neem can be grouped into two major sections: isoprenoids and non-isoprenoids (Tiwari *et al.*, 2014). Isoprenoids are usually in a form of aldehyde, alcohol, ester, ether, and ketone (Waterhouse *et al.*, 2016), yet for neem, the active compounds are in the form of diterpenoids and triterpenoids (Sarkar *et al.*, 2021). Non-isoprenoids that have been investigated consist of amino acids, polysaccharides, tannins, coumarin, dihydrochalcone, polyphenolic compounds, sulphurous compounds and aliphatic compounds (Shah *et al.*, 2009).

Among the notable isoprenoid constituents, terpenes play a vital role as they have been extensively studied and are known for their pesticidal and medicinal properties (Simmonds *et al.*, 2004; Chaudhary *et al.*, 2017; Braga *et al.*, 2020; Lin *et al.*, 2021; Lin *et al.*, 2022). Terpenes found in neem include Azadirachtin, Azadirone (from the oil), Gedunin (from the seed oil and bark), Meliacarpin, Nimbin (from the leaves and seed), Salannin (from the leaves and seed), and Vilasinin (from the green leaves). They can be further classified as triterpenoids and, specifically, limonins, which are known for their antifeedant properties against insect pests. From the active compounds being studied, it is believed that these triterpenoids contribute to anthelmintic effects.

Anthelmintic Potential of *Azadirachta indica*

Research on the anthelmintic properties of *A. indica* has explored the various parts of the plant, including leaves, seeds, aerial parts, and flowers (Table 3). However, the leaf part of *A. indica* has been primarily investigated for its anthelmintic ability due to the readily available nature of the leaves throughout its lifecycle. Different forms of *A. indica* extracts have shown promising results in controlling some nematodes in different species of domesticated animals. *Haemonchus contortus*, commonly known as the "barber pole" worm, is one of the major species of parasitic nematodes affecting ruminants, particularly sheep and goats, causing haemonchosis. The methanolic leaf extract of *A. indica* exhibited a dose- and time-dependent response in reducing the egg per gram (EPG) fecal content of infected goats over the course of 3-week treatment (Priscilla *et al.*, 2014). Similarly, the water extract of *A. indica* showed a time- and dose-dependent response, resulting in 89% reduction in EPG fecal content in infected sheep 12 days post-treatment (Nawaz *et al.*, 2014). The ethanol extract of the aerial parts of *A. indica* also demonstrated an ovicidal effect on *H. contortus* eggs, inhibiting 97.77% of egg development at a concentration of 3.12 mg/ml (Costa *et al.*, 2008). Additionally, the ethanolic seed extract of *A. indica* produced 93% mortality rate for exsheathed third-stage larvae of *H. contortus*. This effect was observed even at the lowest concentration tested, which is 1.3 µg/µl (Hördegen *et al.*, 2006).

Fasciolosis is a widespread parasitic disease occurring in livestock, mainly caused by *Fasciola hepatica* and *Fasciola gigantica*. Different parts of *A. indica* have been explored for anthelmintic ability against these parasitic worms (Table 3). 10 mg/ml aqueous extract of *A. indica* leaves has been shown to eradicate *F. hepatica* over a 3-hour period *in vitro* (Ibekwe, 2019). In contrast, the ethanol extract was shown to be ineffective according to motility score interpretation criteria when tested against *Fasciola sp.* in infected buffalo liver (Yamson *et al.*, 2019). The oil extract from dried neem seeds also did not cause significant motility against *F. gigantica in vitro* (Jeyathilakan *et al.*, 2010).

A. indica has also been tested against the roundworm species *Ascaridia galli*, a parasitic roundworm causing helminth infection in chickens. The aqueous extract of *A. indica* at 40 mg/ml significantly demonstrated maximum efficacy in the mortality of *A. galli* (Rabiou & Subhasish, 2011). Moreover, n-hexane seed extract of *A. indica* also exhibited the ability to eliminate and inhibit the development of eggs to larvae at 20 mg/ml (Hellawi & Ibrahim, 2020). The trematode parasite, *Gastrothylax indicus*, was exposed to ethanolic and aqueous extracts of *A. indica*, and both extracts at 50 mg/ml caused significant anthelmintic effects at 4 hours post exposure (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2016). Both extracts were also shown to produce worm motility

inhibition of 89.6 % (Aggarwal *et al.*, 2016). It is believed that the extract might alter the enzymes responsible for the normal metabolism of the absorptive surface on the treated worm. Furthermore, extracts from different parts of neem have been tested for their antiparasitic activities against species other than helminths. Maran *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that the leaf aqueous extract of *A. indica* exhibited effectiveness against the marine parasitic leech *Zeylanicobdella arugamensis*. The total mortality of leeches was noticed with exposure to the *A. indica* aqueous extract in a dose-dependent manner. All leeches were eliminated in an average period of 6.45 ± 0.45 min (100 mg/mL), 11.69 ± 1.11 min (50 mg/mL), and 42.65 ± 9.20 min (25 mg/mL). Additionally, petroleum ether flower extract of *A. indica* was shown to cause paralysis in adult earthworms at a concentration of 40 mg/ml (Salma *et al.*, 2021).

***Andrographis paniculata* (HEMPEDU BUMI)**

Andrographis paniculata (family: Acanthaceae) (Table 1) is an annual, branching, herbaceous plant that grows to a height of 30 to 110 cm. It is characterised by its slender green stems, vivid green, lance-shaped leaves measuring approximately 8 cm in length and 2 cm in width. *A. paniculata* is commonly known as Hempedu Bumi in Malaysia/Brunei and Kalmegha in India (Table 2).

A. paniculata is native to Taiwan, Mainland China, and India. It is also commonly found in tropical Asian countries including Malaysia, Indonesia, and Brunei. Traditional medicinal practices have long utilised *A. paniculata* to treat various ailments such as bronchitis, worm infestation, influenza, dyspepsia, flatulence, and diarrhea (Maiti *et al.*, 2006; Okhwarobo *et al.*, 2014; Sharma and Sanadhya, 2017). This herb is popularly known as the "King of bitters" due to its distinctive bitter taste.

Phytochemistry of *Andrographis paniculata*

The bioactive components of *A. paniculata* generally consist of lactones, diterpenoids, flavonoids, quinic acid, xanthenes, and noriridoids (Rao *et al.*, 2004; Xu *et al.*, 2010; Hossain *et al.*, 2021). Andrographolide emerges as the main constituent of diterpenoids in *A. paniculata* and is found abundant constituting 15% of the extract (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021). The derivatives of the Andrographolide were also detected in this plant which are deoxyandrographolide, neoandrographolide, 14-deoxy-11,12-didehydroandrographide and isoandrographolide (Chao *et al.*, 2010). Andrographolide exhibits multiple pharmacological properties and is a potential chemotherapeutic agent.

Andrographolide and its derivatives have been recognised as effective natural compounds for use as pesticides. The compounds exhibit various modes of actions and interactions against different pest species. For instance, andrographolide acts as an antifeedant against *Plutella xylostella* and *Helicoverpa armigera*, similar to the limonins found in *A. indica* (Hermawan *et al.*, 1993; Ramya *et al.*, 2008). Edwin *et al.* (2021) also demonstrated the antifeedant effect of andrographolide, resulting in a change in the enzymatic profile of the insect pests, *Spodoptera litura* (Edwin *et al.*, 2021). Different fractions of *A. paniculata* extracts have also been found to possess insecticidal and repellent properties against *Tribolium castaneum* and *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Adekunle and Ayodele, 2014; Baliyarsingh *et al.*, 2021).

Anthelmintic Potential of *Andrographis paniculata*

The leaves and roots of *A. paniculata* extracts have shown to have anthelmintic activity against different parasites (Table 3). Banerjee *et al.* (2019) investigated the anthelmintic properties of *A. paniculata* extracts by focusing on the ovicidal and larvicidal activities against *Ancylostoma duodenale*. Both ethanol and methanol extracts of the *A. paniculata* leaves exhibited significant inhibition of egg hatching in *A. duodenale* (Human hookworm) with median effective dose (ED₅₀) of 0.017 mg/ml and 0.02 mg/ml, respectively. Meanwhile, ethyl acetate and ethanol extracts demonstrated the highest larvicidal activity with half-maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values of 0.001 mg/ml and 0.0019 mg/ml, respectively. The andrographolide component in the extracts is one of the main phytochemicals responsible for significant inhibitory effects both on ovicidal and larvicidal activities against field isolates of *A. duodenale* (Banerjee *et al.*, 2019).

Another study by Kamaraj *et al.* (2011) showed that the methanolic leaf extract of *A. paniculata* was as effective as Albendazole and Ivermectin in preventing the hatching of eggs and inhibiting larval development of *H. contortus* at a concentration of 25 mg/ml. Similarly, Singh *et al.* (2011) demonstrated that treatment of *H. contortus* eggs with *A. paniculata* aqueous leaf extract significantly inhibited egg hatching at a concentration of 1.25 mg/ml. However, moderate larvicidal activity (43.58%) was observed at a concentration of 20 mg/ml post 72 hours of treatment with the extract.

When tested against parasitic worms *Ascaris lumbricoide*, the ethanolic plant extract of *A. paniculata* was significantly paralysed and killed the parasitic worms (Raj, 1975). Similarly, the ethanolic leaf extract of *A. paniculata* exhibited a time- and dose- dependent response in the mortality of nematode from the same genus of different species, *Ascaris suum*, achieving complete eradication at 80% concentration within 5.89 ± 5.84 hours (Chastity *et al.*, 2015).

Both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *A. paniculata* demonstrated significant paralysis and mortality against the earthworm *Pheretima prosthuma*, with a maximum effective inhibitory concentration of 50 mg/ml for both extracts (Murali *et al.*, 2014). The finding also showed that *A. paniculata* exhibits potent anthelmintic activity when compared to the standard drug, albendazole (Murali *et al.*, 2014). Dutta and Sukul (1982) studied the efficacy of the aqueous extract of *A. paniculata* leaves against the microfilariae, *Dipetalonema reconditum* in dogs, and it was found that the extract was able to reduce more than 85% of microfilariae at a dosage of 0.06 ml per kg of body weight. Additionally, the ethyl acetate *A. paniculata* leaf extract showed a toxic effect on *Paramphistomum cervi* (sheep fluke), with lethal concentration 50 (LC50) value of 0.45 mg/ml (Elango and Rahuman, 2011).

***Clitoria ternatea* (TELANG)**

Clitoria ternatea, commonly known as Butterfly pea or Telang in Malay is a perennial herbaceous plant from the Fabaceae family. (Table 1 and Table 2). It usually grows as a vine or creeper that thrives in moist and neutral soil conditions. One of its distinctive features is the striking vivid deep blue flowers which resemble butterflies, where the outer petals display a predominant blue hue that gradually transforms into whitish or yellowish tones towards the center. The plant has compound odd-pinnate leaves that are alternately arranged with 5-7 elliptic or ovate leaflets. *C. ternatea* produces fruit pods which resembles peas, that undergo a transformation into a pale brown shade upon reaching maturity.

Clitoria ternatea is native to tropical Asia and widely distributed in India, South and Central America, the Caribbean, and Madagascar (Lakshan *et al.*, 2019). The genus *Clitoria* encompasses several species, with many known for their traditional medicinal properties, specifically in the realm of reproductive health, libido enhancement, and the treatment of gonorrhea (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2008). *C. ternatea* has long been widely used as a brain tonic and is believed to promote memory and intelligence (Talpate *et al.*, 2013).

In Malay culture, the flower of *C. ternatea* holds cultural significance and practical applications. The juice extracted from its vibrant flowers serves as a natural dye, imparting a distinctive blue colour to a signature rice dish, adding visual appeal to culinary traditions. Additionally, the flower juice can be used as a treatment for snake bites (Sahu *et al.*, 2023). Furthermore, the roots of Butterfly pea are believed to exhibit valuable medicinal properties, offering potential relief for conditions such as ascites, abdominal viscera enlargement, skin diseases, and sore throat (Al-Snafi, 2016).

Phytochemistry of *Clitoria ternatea*

The potential of *C. ternatea* as an anthelmintic candidate is supported by phytochemical studies that found several active ingredients such as tannins, plobatins, saponins, triterpenoids, phenols, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthraquinones, anthocyanins, flavonols, resins, glycosides, steroids, essential oils, and cholestenones (Manjula *et al.*, 2013; Jeyaraj *et al.*, 2021; Siddham *et al.*, 2023). GC-MS analysis identified 30 compounds in *C. ternatea*, with the main predicted compounds being Butyl-2-ethyl-hexyl-phthalate (30.19%), Butyl-2-methyl-propylphthalate (20.11%), Butyl-2-methylpropylphthalate (10.39%), and Butyloctyl-phthalate (11.29%) (Thakur *et al.*, 2018).

Out of the several bioactive compounds of *C. ternatea* being mentioned, the peptide-based compounds exhibit significant importance in pest control and as potential anthelmintics. Finotin, a protein extracted from the seeds was found to cause 100% larvae mortality in bruchids *Zabrotes subfasciatus* and *Acanthoscelidius obtectus* at 5% and 1% dosage, respectively (Kelemu *et al.*, 2004). Another plant-derived peptide compound with insecticidal properties is cyclotides, which are often utilised by plants for defence mechanisms. The cyclotide Cter M, exhibited mortality in L3 larvae of *Helicoverpa armigera* at a concentration of 1 μmol peptide/g diet (Poth *et al.*, 2011). This finding correlates with other studies on cyclotides, demonstrating their insecticidal properties in various plant families (Jennings *et al.*, 2001; Barbeta *et al.*, 2008; Colgrave *et al.*, 2008).

Anthelmintic Potential of *Clitoria ternatea*

Few studies have been conducted on the anthelmintic potential of *C. ternatea* extracts in combating parasitic nematodes and other similar organisms (Table 3). Khadatkar *et al.* (2008) demonstrated that the crude ethanolic extract, petroleum ether fraction, ethyl acetate fraction and methanol fraction of *C. ternatea* exhibited significant motility and mortality against non-nematodes, the annelid *P. posthuma* at a concentration of 50 mg/ml. Similarly, Nirmal *et al.* (2008) conducted a study using different parts of the plant, including flowers, leaves, stem, and roots, and found that the methanol root extract of *C. ternatea* demonstrated the highest potency as compared to other plant parts at a concentration of 20 mg/ml when tested against *P. posthuma*. The study is also in concordance with Shekhawat and Vijayvergia (2011), which demonstrated a time- and dose-dependent efficacy in the motility and mortality of the earthworm, with the maximum dose of 100 mg/ml for complete mortality post treatment with the plant's ethanolic extract. Another study focused on the different species of earthworm, *Eisenia fetida*, and reported the significant effects on the motility and mortality of *E. fetida* at

a concentration of 100 mg/ml for both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *C. ternatea* (Salhan *et al.*, 2011).

***Litsea elliptica* (PAWAS)**

Litsea elliptica, of the Lauraceae family (Table 1), is a plant that holds significance both as a culinary ingredient and in traditional medicine. Locally known as Pawas or Madang Pawas (Table 2) in Brunei, the plant is characterised as a tall tree, that can reach a height of up to 30 meters. The bark of the tree displays a smooth texture and is grey brown in colour, while the inner bark exhibits a pinkish hue. The leaves are green, elliptic in shape, and are arranged alternately, with a leathery texture. Young shoots of *L. elliptica* exhibit a striking reddish-maroon colour, and the leaves will emit an aromatic fragrance when crushed. The leaves of *L. elliptica* are often susceptible to gall attacks in the wild (Ngearnsaengsaruy *et al.*, 2011; de Kok, 2021).

L. elliptica, particularly the young shoots are commonly consumed as salads (ulam) by the local community, in addition to its utilisation for therapeutic purposes. Traditional applications include the treatment of headaches, fever, and stomach ulcers (Grosvenor *et al.*, 1995; Taib *et al.*, 2009; Goh *et al.*, 2022). In addition, *L. elliptica* has been reported to reduce the incidence of gastric cancer (Bhamarapravati *et al.*, 2003; Taib *et al.*, 2009). Modern pharmacological studies of *Litsea elliptica* have demonstrated its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties (Wong *et al.*, 2014).

Phytochemistry of *Litsea elliptica*

A comprehensive investigation conducted by Goh *et al.* (2022) explored the phytochemical composition of methanolic extracts derived from young leaves and mixed leaves of *L. elliptica*, where the identified secondary metabolite groups consist of various compounds, including aliphatic alcohol, aromatic alcohols, coumaran, cyclic alcohol, fatty acid ester, diterpene, phthalic acid monoester, flavonoid, phenolics, furaldehyde, furanone, terpene, triterpene, and sesquiterpenoids. Notably, four groups among the identified compounds have been demonstrated to possess pesticidal or nematicidal properties, namely aliphatic alcohol, aromatic alcohols, fatty acids, and triterpenes. Aromatic alcohols such as catechol and pyrogallol are commercially utilised as precursors for pesticides, highlighting their potential pesticidal activity (Lim *et al.*, 2009). In the aliphatic alcohol group, heptacosan-1-ol exhibited promising efficacy, surpassing the nematicide *A. indica*, when the ethanolic extract of the aerial

parts of another plant, *Buddleja crispa* having this compound was tested against the nematode *Meloidogyne incognita* (Sultana *et al.*, 2010).

Among the fatty acid group, hexadecanoic acid, a soap concentrate insecticide and acaricide, has been employed to control soft-bodied insects such as aphids, mealybugs, and thrips (Lewis *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the triterpene squalene demonstrated significant mortality against the adult *Melanaphis sacchari* at a concentration of 2.5 mg/ml (Sotelo-Leyva *et al.*, 2023). The presence of phytochemical compounds in *L. elliptica*, particularly those exhibiting the potential as pesticidal and nematicidal properties, requires further study, as the potential bioactive compounds derived from the plant to combat pests and parasitic worms are still lacking.

Anthelmintic Potential of *Litsea elliptica*

Although the anthelmintic properties based on the active constituents of *L. elliptica* are still lacking, insights into its potential anthelmintic activity can be extrapolated from the active constituents reported from previous studies, as well as anthelmintic investigations conducted on other species within the same genus, *Litsea*. *In vitro* studies revealed that the methanolic leaf extract of *Litsea monopetala* was effective in causing a reduction in the motility and mortality of adult earthworms, specifically *P. posthuma*, with the most effective inhibitory concentration observed at 60 mg/ml (Mohammad, 2021; Dewanjee *et al.*, 2022).

Essential oils extracted from the fruit of *Litsea cubeba* also exhibited significant mortality at an LC₅₀ value of 0.504 mg/ml when tested against the Pine Wood nematode, *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* (Park *et al.*, 2007). The major constituents of the essential oil contributing to such effects were identified as Limonene (14.64%), Neral (30.27%), and Geranial (39.23%) (Park *et al.*, 2007).

In the case of *Litsea elliptica*, it was reported to have potential insecticidal activities against three mosquito species: *Anopheles maculatus*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Jantan *et al.*, 1996). The essential oil extracted from the leaves exhibited an impact on the larval survival of all three mosquito species, with LC₅₀ values of 13.61 µg/ml, 16.01 µg/ml, and 14.63 µg/ml, respectively (Jantan *et al.*, 1996). An aqueous cream with 1/3 essential oils from *L. elliptica* has a protective role up to 96.6% against mosquito bites (Ibrahim and Zaridah, 1998). Additionally, the methanol fraction of *L. elliptica* leaves has been shown to control the vector of dengue fever (Hidayatulfathi *et al.*, 2004). Although direct anthelmintic studies focusing specifically on *L. elliptica* are still limited, the available evidence from previous studies on other *Litsea* species related to their anthelmintic and insecticidal properties

suggests that *Litsea elliptica* can be a potential candidate to fight against helminth parasites. Furthermore, the presence of the active compounds of *Litsea elliptica* needs to be further investigated to understand the potential active constituents contributing to such effects.

Table 3

Summary of the studies done from the medicinal plants: A. indica, A. paniculata, C. ternatea and Litsea sp. on nematodes and other organisms.

Plant species	Plant parts	Extraction Solvent	Assay	Species Tested	MEIC	Remarks	Reference
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Methanol	EPG	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	0.5ml/kg	<i>In vivo</i> test in goats	Priscilla <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Water	EPG	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	2ml/kg	<i>In vivo</i> test in sheep	Nawaz <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>A. indica</i>	AeP	Ethanol	ES	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	3.12mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Costa <i>et al.</i> , 2008
<i>A. indica</i>	SD	Ethanol	LS	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	1.3µg/µl	<i>In vitro</i> studies	Hördegen <i>et al.</i> , 2006
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Water	M/M	<i>Fasciola hepatica</i>	10mg/ml	<i>In vivo</i> test in cattle	Ibekwe, 2019
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Ethanol	M/M	<i>Fasciola sp.</i>	Unspecified (-)	Worm paralysed but not dead	Yamson <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>A. indica</i>	SD	Essential oil	M/M	<i>Fasciola gigantica</i>	Unspecified (-)	<i>In vitro</i> No significance in motility	Jeyathilakan <i>et al.</i> , 2010
<i>A. indica</i>	SD	Isolate	M/M	<i>Rotylenchulus reniformis</i>	0.096mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Sharma <i>et al.</i> , 2003
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Water	M/M	<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	40mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Rabiu and Subhasish, 2011
<i>A. indica</i>	SD	n-hexane	ES	<i>Ascaridia galli</i>	20mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Hellawi & Ibrahim., 2020
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Ethanol and water	M/M	<i>Gastrothylax indicus</i>	50mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Aggarwal <i>et al.</i> , 2016
<i>A. indica</i>	L	Water	M/M	<i>Zeylanicobdella arugamensis</i>			Maran <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>A. indica</i>	Fl	Petroleum Ether	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	40mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Salma <i>et al.</i> , 2021
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Ethanol and methanol	ES	<i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i>	0.017mg/ml, 0.02mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Banerjee <i>et al.</i> , 2019

<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Ethyl acetate and Ethanol	M/M	<i>Ancylostoma duodenale</i>	0.001mg/ml, 0.0019mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Banerjee <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Methanol	ES and LS	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	25mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Kamaraj <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Water	ES and LS	<i>Haemonchus contortus</i>	1.25mg/ml, 20mg/ml	Moderate larvicidal activity at 20mg/ml	Singh <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>A. paniculata</i>	AeP + Rt	Ethanol	M/M	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	Unspecified (-)	<i>In vitro</i> study	Raj, 1975
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Ethanol	M/M	<i>Ascaris suum</i>	80% concentrate from ethanol extract	<i>In vitro</i> study	Chastity <i>et al.</i> , 2015
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Water and ethanol	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	50mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Murali <i>et al.</i> , 2014
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Water	M/M	<i>Dipetalonima reconditum</i>	0.06ml/kg	<i>In vivo</i> study	Dutta & Sukul, 1982
<i>A. paniculata</i>	L	Ethyl acetate	M/M	<i>Paramphistomum cervi</i>	LC ₅₀ 0.45mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Elango and Rahuman, 2011
<i>C. ternatea</i>	Rt	Ethanol, ethyl acetate and methanol	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	50mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Khadatkar <i>et al.</i> , 2008
<i>C. ternatea</i>	Rt	Methanol	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	20mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Nirmal <i>et al.</i> , 2008
<i>C. ternatea</i>	AeP + Rt	Ethanol	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	100mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Shekhawat and Vijayvergia, 2011
<i>C. ternatea</i>	L	Water and ethanol	M/M	<i>Eisenia fetida</i>	100mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Salhan <i>et al.</i> , 2011
<i>L. monopetal a</i>	L	Methanol	M/M	<i>Pheretima posthuma</i>	60mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Mohammad, 2021
<i>L. cubeba</i>	Fr	Essential oil	M/M	<i>Bursaphelenchus xylophilus</i>	LC ₅₀ 0.504mg/ml	<i>In vitro</i> study	Park <i>et al.</i> , 2007

AeP: Aerial parts, L: Leaves, SD: Seed, Fl: Flower, Rt: root, Fr: fruit, EPG: Egg Per gram, ES: Egg survival/ovicidal, LS: larval survival, M/M: Motility and mortality, MEIC: Most Effective Inhibitory concentration

Future directions

Plants may serve as an alternative source to combat helminth parasites due to their richness in bioactive chemicals, effective against a number of species, including specific target-parasitic nematodes, and are biodegradable. This review aims to summarise the anthelmintic properties of selected Brunei medicinal plants: *A. indica*, *A. paniculata*, *C. ternatea* and *L. elliptica* with the association of active chemical compounds contributing to the detrimental effects against helminth parasites. The review identifies several future directions for enhancing our understanding and utilization of plant based-anthelmintics.

Isolation and Characterization of Active compounds

Most conducted research has utilised various parts of the plants with different solvent extracts to evaluate their anthelmintic properties. Yet, there has been a scarcity of studies specifically on investigating the exact phytochemical compounds of the extracts having anthelmintic effects. Previous studies primarily examined the phytochemical composition, which are often encompassing a wide range of secondary metabolites, with only rare instances involving the isolation and characterisation of specific active constituents to test their effectiveness against parasitic nematodes. Therefore, a detailed exploration into the chemical constituents of the plants is crucial to enhance our understanding of their anthelmintic potential by isolating the necessary compound. Each species may harbour unique analogues and derivatives of bioactive compounds that have yet to be isolated and evaluated for their anthelmintic properties. By exploring these untapped sources, potential anthelmintic agents can be discovered, contributing to the development of novel treatments against nematode parasitic infections.

Metabolic Pathway Exploration

The underlying mechanisms of action for the anthelmintic of the plants remain largely speculative although efforts have been made to identify the specific stages of the parasite's lifecycle targeted by the plant extracts (Kumarasingha *et al.*, 2016). However, establishing the metabolic responses induced by the extracts in the target organisms has proven challenging due to inherent limitations in the experimental protocols. Studies often focus on toxicity, motility, and reduction in number of eggs laid by the nematodes, neglecting metabolomics for identifying disruptions caused in the metabolic pathways (Kumarasingha *et al.*, 2016). Utilising parasitic nematodes as test subjects for anthelmintics poses several challenges that complicate experimental design and data interpretation. The availability and maintenance of parasitic nematodes in laboratory settings are complicated, which requires specialised facilities, host animals, and ethical considerations (Gilleard *et al.*, 2021). The complex life cycles of many

parasitic nematodes also involve various developmental stages, making it challenging to synchronize experimental conditions (Perry & Clarke, 1981) and the genetic variability among individual parasitic nematodes within a population may impact the reproducibility of the results (Haag *et al.*, 2018). The intricate interactions between parasitic nematode and its host organism further complicate the isolation of intrinsic nematode responses to anthelmintic treatments. Moreover, the risk of developing anthelmintic resistance in parasitic nematode populations poses a significant concern, potentially limiting the effectiveness of these secondary metabolites over time (Peña-Espinoza *et al.*, 2016).

Alternative Model Organism

These challenges highlight the importance of considering alternative model organisms, such as the non-parasitic nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*, which offers experimental advantages and contributes valuable insights to anthelmintic research without the complexities associated with the parasitic species. *C. elegans* is a free-living nematode that is easy to culture in the laboratory and has a short life cycle of about three days allowing for rapid experimentation and high throughput screening. The transparency of *C. elegans* allows for the easy visualisation of internal organs and processes, facilitating the observation of the effects of secondary metabolites on the nematode's anatomy and physiological changes. This transparency provides valuable insights into the mode of action of anthelmintic compounds (Izquierdo *et al.*, 2021).

Genetic Manipulation Studies

C. elegans is amenable to genetic manipulation, enabling researchers to knock down or overexpress specific genes associated with drug sensitivity or resistance. This genetic tractability allows for the study of molecular mechanisms underlying anthelmintic responses (Sugi, 2016). Notably, many biological processes and pathways are conserved between *C. elegans* and parasitic nematodes, offering relevant information about potential drug targets in parasitic nematodes (International Helminth Genomes Consortium, 2019). The use of *C. elegans* helps circumvent the ethical concerns associated with working directly with parasitic nematodes, especially those infecting humans or animals. This model organism allows researchers to study anthelmintics without causing harm to the hosts or using live animals (Ha *et al.*, 2022). The complete and well-annotated genome of *C. elegans* further facilitates the identification of potential drug targets and enhances our understanding of the molecular basis of anthelmintic action (Sugi, 2016). Various research has been done to investigate the anthelmintic effect on *C. elegans* of the various plants including *Guiera senegalensis* (Gagman *et al.*, 2022), *Leucena leucocephala* (Widaad *et al.*, 2022) and *Rumex crispus* (Idris *et al.*, 2022). Understanding the metabolic pathways that the novel anthelmintic compounds act using

C. elegans can help to combat helminth parasites effectively and overcome modern drug resistance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the review highlights the potential of selected Brunei medicinal plants as alternative anthelmintic sources, particularly noting their effectiveness against nematode parasites due to the presence of the phytochemicals in the plants that contributing to such effect. The review also highlights existing research limitations in identifying specific phytochemical compounds and understanding the underlying mechanisms. The proposed use of *Caenorhabditis elegans* as a model organism to explore the exact active compounds having anthelmintic ability and elucidating the mechanism of action suggest promising avenues for future research to enhance better understanding of plant-based anthelmintics and their potential in combating nematode parasitic infections.

Conflict of interest

We declare that we have no conflict of interest.

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References

- Adekunle, O. A. & Ayodele F. T., (2014). Insecticidal Activity of the Aqueous Leaves Extract of *Andrographis paniculata* as protectant of Cowpea Seeds from *Callosobruchus maculatus* infestation. *Central European Journal of Experimental Biology*, 3(1), 29-33.
- Aggarwal, R., Kaur, K., Suri, M., & Bagai, U. (2016). Anthelmintic potential of *Calotropis procera*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Punica granatum* against *Gastrothylax indicus*. *Journal of Parasitic Diseases*, 40(4), 1230–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12639-015-0658-0>
- Al-Snafi, A. E. (2016). Pharmacological importance of *Clitoria ternatea*-A review. *IOSR Journal of Pharmacy*, 6(3), 68–83.
- Baliyarsingh, B., Mishra, A. & Rath, S. (2021). Evaluation of insecticidal and repellency activity of leaf extracts of *Andrographis paniculata* against *Tribolium castaneum* (red flour beetle). *The International Journal of Tropical Insect Science* 41, 765–773. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-020-00267-9>
- Banerjee, T., Singh, A., Kumar, S., Dhanani, T., Gajbhiye, N. A., Koley, T. K., Maurya, A. & Filgona, J. (2019). Ovicidal and larvicidal effects of extracts from leaves of *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm. F.) Wall.ex Nees against field isolates of human hookworm (*Ancylostoma*

- duodenale*). *Journal of ethnopharmacology*, 235, 489–500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2019.02.021>
- Barbeta, B. L., Marshall, A. T., Gillon, A. D., Craik, D. J., Anderson, M. A. (2008) Plant cyclotides disrupt epithelial cells in the midgut of lepidopteran larvae. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 105:1221–1225.
- Bhamarapravati, S., Pendland, S.L., Mahady, G.B. (2003). Extracts of spice and food plants from Thai traditional medicine inhibit the growth of the human carcinogen *Helicobacter Pylori*. *In Vivo*, 17(6), 541-544.
- Braga, T. M., Rocha, L., Chung, T. Y., Oliveira, R. F., Pinho, C., Oliveira, A. I., Morgado, J., & Cruz, A. (2020). Biological Activities of Gedunin—A Limonoid from the Meliaceae Family. *Molecules*, 25(3), 493. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25030493>
- Chao, W. W., & Lin, B. F. (2010). Isolation and identification of bioactive compounds in *Andrographis paniculata* (Chuanxinlian). *Chinese Medicine*, 5(17), 1–15.
- Charlier, J., van der Voort, M., Kenyon, F., Skuce, P., & Vercruyssen, J. (2014). Chasing helminths and their economic impact on farmed ruminants. *Trends in parasitology*, 30(7), 361-367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2014.04.009>
- Chastity, C. N., Yuwono, K. L., Utami, U., Ap, P. A., Priscillah, W., & Sutrisna, E. (2015). The anthelmintic effect of *Momordica charantia* L. leaves and *Andrographis paniculata* Ness. From Indonesia. *International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research*, 3(6), 33-39.
- Chaudhary, S., Kanwar, R. K., Sehgal, A., Cahill, D. M., Barrow, C. J., Sehgal, R., Kanwar, J. R. (2017). Progress on *Azadirachta indica* Based Biopesticides in Replacing Synthetic Toxic Pesticides. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 8, 610. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2017.00610>.
- Colgrave, M. L., Kotze, A. C., Huang, Y. H., O'Grady, J., Simonsen, S. M., & Craik, D. J. (2008). Cyclotides: natural, circular plant peptides that possess significant activity against gastrointestinal nematode parasites of sheep. *Biochemistry*, 47(20), 5581–5589. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi800223y>
- Costa, C. T. C., Bevilaqua, C. M. L., Camurça-Vasconcelos, A. L. F., Maciel, M. V., Morais, S. M., Castro, C. M. S., Braga, R. R., & Oliveira, L. M. B. (2008). *In vitro* ovicidal and larvicidal activity of *Azadirachta indica* extract on *Haemonchus contortus*. *Small Ruminant Research*, 74(1–3), 284–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.smallrumres.2007.09.003>
- Dutta, A. & Sukul N. C. (1982) Filaricidal properties of a wild herb, *Andrographis paniculata*. *Journal of Helminthology*. 56(2), 81-84. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0022149x0003426x>.
- de Kok, R. P. J. (2021). A revision of *Litsea* (Lauraceae) in Peninsular Malaysia and Singapore. *Gardens' Bulletin Singapore*, 73(1), 81-178. [https://doi.org/10.26492/gbs73\(1\).2021-07](https://doi.org/10.26492/gbs73(1).2021-07)
- Department of Economic Planning and Statistics (2022). *Brunei Darussalam Statistical Yearbook 2022*. Perpustakaan Dewan Bahasa dan Pustaka Brunei
- Dewanjee, S., Akter, F., Hossain, M.S., Islam, M. A., Al Muktedir, M. H., Islam, M. T. & Mahmud, M. K. (2022). *In vitro* cytotoxic, thrombolytic, anthelmintic and antioxidant activities of *Litsea monopetala*: A medicinal plant. *World Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(1), 018–027. <https://doi.org/10.53346/wjcps.2022.1.1.0024>
- Dwivedi, M. K., Sonter, S., Mishra, S., Singh, P. & Singh, P. K. (2021). Secondary metabolite profiling and characterization of diterpenes and flavones from the methanolic extract of *Andrographis paniculata* using HPLC-LC-MS/MS. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 7, 184. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43094-021-00292-6>
- Edwin, E. S., Vasantha-Srinivasan, P., Senthil-Nathan S., Chellappandian, M., Karthi, S., Narayanaswamy, R., Stanley-Raja, V., Sivanesh, H., Ramasubramanian, R., Al-Huqail, A. A., Khan, F., Krutmuang, P., Abdel-Megeed, A., Ghaith, A., Paik, C. H. (2021). Toxicity of Bioactive Molecule Andrographolide against *Spodoptera litura* Fab and Its Binding Potential with

- Detoxifying Enzyme Cytochrome P450. *Molecules*, 26(19), 5982. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26195982>.
- Elango, G. & Rahuman, A. A. (2011) Evaluation of medicinal plant extracts against ticks and fluke. *Parasitology Research*, 108, 513–519. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-010-2090-9>
- Gagman, H. A., Ahmad, H., Him, N. A. I. I. N. & Avicor, S. W. (2022). *In vitro* assessment of deworming potential of *Guiera senegalensis* in Nigerian ethnoveterinary industry using *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Bulletin of the National Research Centre*, 46(3). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42269-021-00689-6>
- Gilleard, J. S., Kotze, A. C., Leathwick, D., Nisbet, A. J., McNeilly, T. N., Besier, B. (2021) A journey through 50 years of research relevant to the control of gastrointestinal nematodes in ruminant livestock and thoughts on future directions. *International Journal for Parasitology*, 51(13-14), 1133-1151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpara.2021.10.007>.
- Goh, M. P. Y., Kamaluddin, A. F., Tan, T. J. L., Yasin, H., Taha, H., Jama, A., & Ahmad, N. (2022). An evaluation of the phytochemical composition, antioxidant and cytotoxicity of the leaves of *Litsea elliptica* Blume – An ethnomedicinal plant from Brunei Darussalam. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 29(1), 304–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.08.097>
- Grosvenor, P. W., Gothard, P. K., McWilliam, N. C., Supriono, A., Gray, D. O. (1995). Medicinal plants from Riau Province, Sumatra, Indonesia. Part 1: Uses. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 45(2), 75-95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741\(94\)01209-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-8741(94)01209-1)
- Ha, N. M., Tran, S. H., Shim, Y. H., & Kang, K. (2022). *Caenorhabditis elegans* as a powerful tool in natural product bioactivity research. *Applied Biological Chemistry*, 65(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13765-022-00685-y>
- Haag, E. S., Fitch, D. H. A., & Delattre, M. (2018). From “the Worm” to “the Worms” and Back Again: The Evolutionary Developmental Biology of Nematodes. *Genetics*, 210(2), 397–433. <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.118.300243>
- Haji, A. S., Maurya, S. R., Shah, N. (2023). *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss.: Ethnobotanical knowledge, phytochemical studies, pharmacological aspects future prospects. *Plants and Environment* 5(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.22271/2582-3744.2023.mar.1>.
- Hellawi, H., & Ibrahim, O. M. S. (2020). Evaluation of anthelmintic activity of N-hexane extract of *Cucurbita maxima* and *Azadirachta indica* pulp seeds against *Ascaridia galli* In Vitro. *Biochemical and Cellular Archives*, 21(1), 211–217.
- Hermawan, W., Tsukuda, R., Fujisaki, K., Kobayashi, A., Nakasuji, F. (1993). Influence of crude extracts from a tropical plant, *Andrographis paniculata* (Acanthaceae), on suppression of feeding by the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (Lepidoptera: Yponomeutidae) and oviposition by the azuki bean weevil, *Callosobruchus chinensis* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *Applied Entomology and Zoology*, 28(2), 251–254. <https://doi.org/10.1303/aez.28.251>
- Hidayatulfathi, O., Sallehuddin, S., & Ibrahim, J. (2004). Adulticidal activity of some Malaysian plant extracts against *Aedes aegypti* Linnaeus. *Tropical biomedicine*, 21(2), 61–67.
- Hoon, C., Zhao, K., Lim, G. (2023, August 31). “Brunei engages Chinese investment amid diversification challenges”: *The East Asia Forum*. <https://doi.org/10.59425/eabc.1693519208>
- Hördegen, P., Cabaret, J., Hertzberg, H., Langhans, W., & Maurer, V. (2006). *In vitro* screening of six anthelmintic plant products against larval *Haemonchus contortus* with a modified methyl-thiazolyl-tetrazolium reduction assay. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 108(1), 85–89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2006.04.013>
- Hossain, M. S., Urbi, Z., Sule, A., Hafizur Rahman, K. M. (2014). *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm. F.) Wall. Ex Nees: a review of ethnobotany, phytochemistry, and pharmacology. *Scientific World Journal*, 2014, 274905. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/274905>.

- Hossain, S., Urbi, Z., Karuniawati, H., Mohiuddin, R. B., Moh Qrimida, A., Allzrag, A. M. M., Ming, L. C., Pagano, E., Capasso, R. (2021) *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm. F.) Wall. Ex Nees: An Updated Review of Phytochemistry, Antimicrobial Pharmacology, and Clinical Safety and Efficacy. *Life*, 11(4), 348. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life11040348>
- Ibekwe, H. A. (2019). *In vitro* anthelmintic activities of aqueous crude extract of *Azadirachta indica* on *Paramphistomum cervi* and *Fasciola hepatica*. *International Journal of Veterinary Sciences and Animal Husbandry*, 4(1), 14–18.
- Ibrahim, J., & Zaridah, M. Z. (1998) Development of environment-friendly insect repellents from the leaf oils of selected Malaysian plants. *ASEAN Rev. Biodiversity and Env. Conservation (ARBEC)*, 6: 1-7
- Idris, O. A., Wintola, O. A., Afolayan, A. J. (2022) Anthelmintic potency of *Rumex crispus* L. extracts against *Caenorhabditis elegans* and non-targeted identification of the bioactive compounds. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 29(1), 541-549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2021.09.026>.
- International Helminth Genomes Consortium (2019). Comparative genomics of the major parasitic worms. *Nature genetics*, 51(1), 163–174. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-018-0262-1>
- Izquierdo, P. G., O'Connor, V., Green, A. C., Holden-Dye, L., & Tattersall, J. E. H. (2021). *C. elegans* pharyngeal pumping provides a whole organism bio-assay to investigate anti-cholinesterase intoxication and antidotes. *NeuroToxicology*, 82, 50-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuro.2020.11.001>.
- Jantan, I., Zaki, Z. M., & Ahmad, R. (1996). Larvicidal Properties of the Essential Oils of Some Malaysian Plants on Three Vector Mosquitoes. *Pertanika Journal of Science & Technology*, 4(1), 51-55.
- Jennings, C., West, J., Waive, C., Craik, D., Anderson, M. (2001). Biosynthesis and insecticidal properties of plant cyclotides: The cyclic knotted proteins from *Oldenlandia affinis*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 98(19), 10614–10619. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.191366898>
- Jeyaraj, E. J., Lim, Y. Y., & Choo, W. S. (2021). Extraction methods of butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea*) flower and biological activities of its phytochemicals. *Journal of food science and technology*, 58(6), 2054–2067. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13197-020-04745-3>
- Jeyathilakan, N., Murali, K., Anandaraj, A., Latha, B. R. & Abdul Basith, S. (2010). Anthelmintic activity of essential oils of *Cymbopogon nardus* and *Azadirachta indica* on *Fasciola gigantica*. *Tamil Nadu Journal of Veterinary and Animal Sciences*, 6(5), 204-209.
- Kamaraj, C., Rahuman, A. A., Elango, G., Bagavan, A., & Zahir, A. A. (2011). Anthelmintic activity of botanical extracts against sheep gastrointestinal nematodes, *Haemonchus contortus*. *Parasitology Research*, 109(1), 37–45. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00436-010-2218-y>
- Kaplan, R. M. (2004). Drug resistance in nematodes of veterinary importance: a status report. *Trends in parasitology*, 20(10), 477-481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pt.2004.08.001>
- Kelemu, S., Cardona, C., & Segura, G. (2004). Antimicrobial and insecticidal protein isolated from seeds of *Clitoria ternatea*, a tropical forage legume. *Plant physiology and biochemistry*, 42(11), 867–873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2004.10.013>
- Khadatkar, S. N., Manwar, J. V., & Bhajipale, N. S. (2008). *In-vitro* anthelmintic activity of root of *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. *Pharmacognosy Magazine*, 4(13), 148–150.
- Kumar, V. S., Navaratnam, V. (2013). Neem (*Azadirachta indica*): prehistory to contemporary medicinal uses to humankind. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 3(7), 505–514. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691\(13\)60105-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691(13)60105-7)
- Kumarasingha, R., Karpe, A. V., Preston, S., Yeo, T. C., Lim, D. S. L., Tu, C. L., Luu, J., Simpson, K. J., Shaw, J. M., Gasser, R. B., Beale, D. J., Morrison, P. D., Palombo, E. A., & Boag, P. R. (2016). Metabolic profiling and in vitro assessment of anthelmintic fractions of *Picria fel-terrae* Lour.

- International journal for parasitology. Drugs and drug resistance*, 6(3), 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpddr.2016.08.002>
- Lakshan, S. A. T., Jayanath, N. Y., Abeysekera, W. P. K. M., & Abeysekera, W. K. S. M. (2019). A Commercial Potential Blue Pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.) Flower Extract Incorporated Beverage Having Functional Properties. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine: eCAM*, 2019, 2916914. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/2916914>
- Lewis, K. A., Tzilivakis, J., Warner, D. & Green, A. (2016). An international database for pesticide risk assessments and management. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 22(4), 1050-1064. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2015.1133242>
- Lim, E., Pon, A., Djoumbou, Y., Knox, C., Shrivastava, S., Guo, A. C., Neveu, V., Wishart, D. S. (2009) T3DB: a comprehensively annotated database of common toxins and their targets. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 38(Issue suppl_1), D781-D786. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp934>.
- Lin, M., Bi, X., Zhou, L., Huang, J. (2022) Insecticidal Triterpenes in Meliaceae: Plant Species, Molecules, and Activities: Part II (*Cipadessa*, *Melia*). *International Journal of Molecular Science*, 23(10), 5329. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23105329>
- Lin, S., Li, S., Liu, Z., Zhang, L., Wu, H., Cheng, D., Zhang, Z. (2021) Using Azadirachtin to Transform *Spodoptera frugiperda* from Pest to Natural Enemy. *Toxins*, 13(8), 541. <https://doi.org/10.3390/toxins13080541>
- Maiti, K., Gantait, A., Mukherjee, K., Saha, B. P., & Mukherjee, P. K. (2006). Therapeutic potentials of Andrographolide from *Andrographis paniculata*: A review. *Journal of Natural Remedies*, 6(1), 1–13.
- Manjula, P., Mohan, Ch., Sreekanth, D., Keerthi, B., & Devi, B. P. (2013). Phytochemical analysis of *Clitoria ternatea* linn., a valuable medicinal plant. *Journal of Indian Botanical Society.*, 94(3 & 4), 173–178.
- Maran, V. B. A., Josmeh, D., Tan, J. K., Yong, Y. S., & Shah, M. D. (2021). Efficacy of the Aqueous Extract of *Azadirachta indica* Against the Marine Parasitic Leech and Its Phytochemical Profiling. *Molecules*, 26(7), 1908. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26071908>
- Mohammad, N. (2021). A study on *Litsea monopetala* for evaluating its pharmacological properties. *Discovery Phytomedicine*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.15562/phytomedicine.2021.159>
- Mukherjee, P. K., Kumar, V., Kumar, N. S., & Heinrich, M. (2008). The Ayurvedic medicine *Clitoria ternatea*-From traditional use to scientific assessment. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 120(3), 291-301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2008.09.009>
- Murali, J., Maheswari, R., Syed Muzammil, M., & Asogan, G. (2014). Anthelmintic activity of leaves extract of *Andrographis paniculata* Nees. *International Journal of Pharmacognosy*, 1(6), 404–408. [https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.IJP.1\(6\).404-08](https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.IJP.1(6).404-08)
- Nawaz, M., Sajid, S. M., Zubair, M., & Ahmed, Z. (2014). *In vitro* and *In vivo* Anthelmintic Activity of Leaves of *Azadirachta indica*, *Dalbergia sisso* and *Morus alba* Against *Haemonchus contortus*. *Global Veterinaria*, 13(6), 996–1001. <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.gv.2014.13.06.9154>
- Ngearnsaengsaruy, C., Middleton, D. J., & Chayamarit, K. (2011). A revision of the genus *Litsea* Lam. (Lauraceae) in Thailand. *Thai Forest Bulletin (Botany)*, (39), 40–119.
- Nicoletti M. (2020). New solutions using natural products. *Insect-Borne Diseases in the 21st Century*, 263–351. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-818706-7.00007-3>
- Nirmal, S. A., Bhalke, R. D., Jadhav, R. S., & Tambe, V. D. (2008). Anthelmintic activity of *Clitoria ternatea*. *Pharmacologyonline*, 1, 114–119.
- Okhuarobo, A., Ehizogie Falodun, J., Erharuyi, O., Imieje, V., Falodun, A., & Langer, P. (2014). Harnessing the medicinal properties of *Andrographis paniculata* for diseases and beyond: A review of its phytochemistry and pharmacology. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*, 4(3), 213–222. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2222-1808\(14\)60509-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2222-1808(14)60509-0)

- Park, I. K., Kim, J., Lee, S. G., Shin, S. C. (2007). Nematicidal Activity of Plant Essential Oils and Components from Ajowan (*Trachyspermum ammi*), Allspice (*Pimenta dioica*) and Litsea (*Litsea cubeba*) Essential Oils Against Pine Wood Nematode (*Bursaphelenchus Xylophilus*). *Journal of Nematology*, 39(3), 275-279.
- Peña-Espinoza, M., Thamsborg, S. M., Denwood, M. J., Drag, M., Hansen, T. V., Jensen, V. F., & Enemark, H. L. (2016). Efficacy of ivermectin against gastrointestinal nematodes of cattle in Denmark evaluated by different methods for analysis of faecal egg count reduction. *International journal for parasitology: Drugs and drug resistance*, 6(3), 241–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpddr.2016.10.004>
- Perry, R. N., & Clarke, A. J. (1981). Hatching mechanisms of nematodes. *Parasitology*, 83(2), 435–449. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0031182000085413>
- Poth, A. G., Colgrave, M. L., Philip, R., Kerenga, B., Daly, N. L., Anderson, M. A., Craik, D. J. (2011) Discovery of Cyclotides in the Fabaceae Plant Family Provides New Insights into the Cyclization, Evolution, and Distribution of Circular Proteins. *ACS Chemical Biology*, 6(4), 345-355. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cb100388j>
- Priscilla, F. X., Amin, M. R., & Rahman, S. (2014). Comparative Study of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Bitter Gourd (*Momordica charantia*) extract as Herbal Anthelmintic and Albendazole as Chemical Anthelmintic in Controlling Gastrointestinal Nematodes in Goats. *IOSR Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, 7(2), 33–37. <https://doi.org/10.9790/2380-07233337>
- Puri, H.S. (1999). *Neem: The Divine Tree Azadirachta indica* (1st ed.). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203304310>
- Rabiu, H. & Subhasish, M. (2011), Investigation of *In Vitro* Anthelmintic activity of *Azadirachta indica* Leaves, *International Journal of Drug Development & Research*, 3(4): 94-100.
- Radzuan, S., Chatwin, C., & Hasan, R. (2022). Tackling Natural Resource Depletion and Revenue Decline through Diversification: The Case of Brunei Darussalam. *South Asian Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(2), 130-138.
- Raj R. K. (1975). Screening of indigenous plants for anthelmintic action against human *Ascaris lumbricoides*: Part II. *Indian journal of physiology and pharmacology*, 19(1)
- Ramya, S., Rajasekaran C., Sundararajan, G., Alaguchamy, N., Jayakumararaj, R. (2008), Antifeedant activity of leaf aqueous extracts of selected medicinal plants on VI instar larva of *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner). *Ethnobotanical Leaflets*, 12, 938–943.
- Rao, Y. K., Vimalamma, G., Rao, C. V., Tzeng, Y. (2004). Flavonoids and andrographolides from *Andrographis paniculata*. *Phytochemistry* 65(16), 2317-2321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phytochem.2004.05.008>
- Sahu, D., Sahu, J. K., Kumar, V., & Tamrakar, S. K. (2023). Phytochemicals and Medicinal Uses of *Clitoria ternatea*. *International Journal of Plant & Soil Science*, 35(18), 942-951.
- Salhan, M., Kumar, B., Tiwari, P., Sharma, P., Sandhar, H. K., & Gautam, M. (2011). Comparative Anthelmintic Activity of Aqueous and Ethanolic Leaf Extracts of *Clitoria ternatea*. *International Journal of Drug Development & Research*. 3(1), 62-69.
- Salma, S. K., Rani, A. M., Indupriya, J., Kumar, V. B. & NagaLakshmi (2021). Biological Evaluation of (*Azadirachta indica*) Neem Flower for Anthelmintic Activity on Earth Worm (*Pheretima posthuma*). *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 13(2), 92–94.
- Sarkar, S., Singh, R. P., & Bhattacharya, G. (2021). Exploring the role of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) and its active compounds in the regulation of biological pathways: an update on molecular approach. *3 Biotech*, 1(4), 178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-021-02745-4>
- Seriana, I., Akmal, M., Darusman, Wahyuni, S., Khairan, Sugito (2021). Phytochemical Characterization of Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) Leaves Ethanolic Extract: An Important Medicinal Plant as Male Contraceptive Candidate. *Rasayan J. Chem.*, 14(1), 343-350.

- Shah, A. S., Gunjal, M. A., & Juvekar, A. R. (2009). Immunostimulatory activity of aqueous extract of *Azadirachta indica* flowers on specific and non-specific immune response. *Journal of Natural Remedies*, 9(1), 35-42.
- Sharma, V., Walia, S., Kumar, J., Nair, M. G., Parmar, B. S. (2003). An efficient method for the purification and characterization of nematicidal azadirachtins A, B, and H, using MPLC and ESIMS. *Journal of Agricultural Food Chemistry*, 51(14), 3966-3972. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0342167>
- Sharma, P., & Sanadhya, D. (2017). The king of bitters, “*Andrographis paniculata*”: A Plant with Multiple Medicinal Properties. *Journal of Plant Science Research*, 33(1), 117–125.
- Shekhawat, N., & Vijayvergia, R. (2011). Anthelmintic Activity of Extracts of Some Medicinal Plants. *International Journal of Computational Science and Mathematics*, 3(2), 183-187
- Siddahm, P., Sonali, R., Jagtap M. N. (2023). Phytochemical Analysis and Antimicrobial Screening of *Clitoria ternatea* L. *Acta Scientific Microbiology*, 6(4), 4-8
- Simmonds, M. S., Jarvis, A. P., Johnson, S., Jones, G. R., Morgan, E. D. (2004). Comparison of anti-feedant and insecticidal activity of nimbin and salannin photo-oxidation products with neem (*Azadirachta indica*) limonoids. *Pest Management Science*. 60(5), 459-464. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.834>
- Singh, D., Swarnkar, C. P., Khan, F. A., Bhagwan, P. S. K. & Dubey, S. C. (2011). *In vitro* ovicidal and larvicidal activity of *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh) leaves on *Haemonchus contortus*. *Indian Journal of Animal Science*, 81(2), 155-157.
- Sotelo-Leyva, C., Toledo-Hernandez, E., Salinas-Sanchez, D. O., Aviles-Montes, D., Silva-Aguayo, G. I., Hernandez-Velazquez, V. M. and Aguilar-Marcelino, L. (2023). Insecticidal potential of pure commercial molecules against the sugarcane aphid *Melanaphis sacchari* (Zehntner). *Southwestern entomologist*, 47(4), 845-852. <https://doi.org/10.3958/059.047.0406>
- Suarna, I. W., & Wijaya, I. M. S. (2021). Butterfly pea (*Clitoria ternatea* L.: Fabaceae) and its morphological variations in Bali. *Journal of Tropical Biodiversity and Biotechnology*, 6(2), 63013. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jtbb.63013>
- Subapriya, R. & Nagini, S. (2005). Medicinal properties of neem leaves: a review. *Current Medicinal Chemistry-Anticancer Agents*, 5(2), 149-156. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1568011053174828>
- Sugi T. (2016). Genome Editing in *C. elegans* and Other Nematode Species. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 17(3), 295. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms17030295>
- Sultana, N., Akhter, M., Khan, R. A., Afza, N., Tareen, R. B., Malik, A. (2010). Nematicidal natural products from the aerial parts of *Buddleja crispa*. *Natural Product Research*, 24(9), 783-788. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786410802496846>
- Taib, I. S., Budin, S. B., Siti Nor Ain, S. M., Mohamed, J., Louis, S. R., Das, S., Sallehudin, S., Rajab, N. F., & Hidayatulfathi, O. (2009). Toxic effects of *Litsea elliptica* Blume essential oil on red blood cells of Sprague-Dawley rats. *Journal of Zhejiang University. Science. B*, 10(11), 813–819. <https://doi.org/10.1631/jzus.B0920199>
- Talpate, K. A., Bhosale, U. A., Zambare, M. R., & Somani, R. (2013). Antihyperglycemic and antioxidant activity of *Clitoria ternatea* Linn. on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. *Ayu*, 34(4), 433–439. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0974-8520.127730>
- Thakur, A. V., Ambwani, S., Ambwani, T. K., Ahmad, A. H., & Rawat, D. S. (2018). Evaluation of phytochemicals in the leaf extract of *Clitoria ternatea* Willd. through GC-MS analysis. *Tropical Plant Research*, 5(2), 200–206. <https://doi.org/10.22271/tpr.2018.v5.i2.025>
- Tiwari, R., Verma, A. K., Chakraborty, S., Dhama, K., & Singh, S. V. (2014). Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) and its potential for safeguarding health of animals and humans: A review. *Journal of Biological Sciences*, 14(2), 110.

- Veerakumari, L. (2015). Botanical anthelmintics. *Asian Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 6, 1881-94.
- Waterhouse, A. L., Sacks, G. L. and Jeffery, D. W. (2016). Isoprenoids. In A.L. Waterhouse, G.L. Sacks and D.W. Jeffery (eds) *Understanding Wine Chemistry*. Wiley <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118730720.ch8>
- Widaad, A., Zulkipli, I. N., & Petalcorin, M. I. R. (2022). Anthelmintic Effect of *Leucaena leucocephala* Extract and Its Active Compound, Mimosine, on Vital Behavioral Activities in *Caenorhabditis elegans*. *Molecules*, 27(6), 1875. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules27061875>
- Wong, M. H., Lim, L. F., Ahmad, F. B., & Assim, Z. B. (2014). Antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of *Litsea elliptica* Blume and *Litsea resinosa* Blume (Lauraceae). *Asian Pacific journal of tropical biomedicine*, 4(5), 386–392. <https://doi.org/10.12980/APJTB.4.2014C1129>
- Wylie, M. R., & Merrell, D. S. (2022). The Antimicrobial Potential of the Neem Tree *Azadirachta indica*. *Frontiers in pharmacology*, 13, 891535. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2022.891535>
- Xu, C., Chou, G. X., Wang, Z. T. (2010) A new diterpene from the leaves of *Andrographis paniculata* Nees. *Fitoterapia*, 81(6), 610-613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fitote.2010.03.003>
- Yakubu, S., Saleh, U. & Abdullahi, G. (2006). In-Vitro Anthelmintic Efficacy of Crude Aqueous Extracts Of Neem (*Azadirachta Indica*) Leaf, Stem And Root On Nematode. *Animal Research International*, 3(3), 549-552. <http://doi.org/10.4314/ari.v3i3.40790>
- Yamson, E. C., Tubalinal, G. A. S. P., Vilorio, V. V., & Mingala, C. N. (2019). Anthelmintic effect of betel nut (*Areca catechu*) and neem (*Azadirachta indica*) extract against liver fluke (*Fasciola* spp.). *Journal of Advanced Veterinary and Animal Research*, 6(1), 44–49. <https://doi.org/10.5455/javar.2019.e310>